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Document Type		
PRO	Technical/economic progress report (internal work package reports indicating work status)	
DEL	Technical reports identified as deliverables in the Description of Work	X
MoM	Minutes of Meeting	
MAN	Procedures and user manuals	
WOR	Working document, issued as preparatory documents to a Technical report	
INF	Information and Notes	

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CON	Confidential, only for members of the Consortium	

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Executive Summary

Deliverable 8.4 within Work Package 8 “Communication, dissemination and clustering” relates to the creation and delivery of a public website for the FishEUTrust project. The main objective of the website is to inform industry, the research community, supply chain and consumers about the project objectives, progress, and new and events. Longer term, the website will also be used to integrate (or link to) the various data platforms that are being developed within the project.

The domain <https://www.fisheustrust.org/> was launched in August 2022 after signature of the grant and collaboration agreement. It should be noted that it was not possible to use a .eu domain due to recent regulations from Brexit restricting UK companies (i.e. WRG Europe Ltd) from registering such domains. Please note that the Coordinator is currently looking to purchase the *.eu domain and then a redirect will set up to the .org site. This means all media and branding can use the .eu domain to be consistent with other EU projects, whilst the primary website can be maintained legitimately within the UK.

This report provides a general description of FishEUTrust website aims, design, and content, as well as plans for site modifications and development.

1. Website Overview

Creating awareness of and engagement with industry (e.g. fish supply chain), the scientific community, consumers, and other related stakeholders (e.g. policymakers) about progress, tools, and exploitable results of FishEUTrust is a critical activity in order to create impact. One of the primary means to achieve this is a project website and is central to the WP8 “Dissemination, communication, and clustering” work package, led by WRG Europe Ltd.

Once the branding (including logo and colourways) had been developed by WRG Europe, the website was built around this branding. The site was launched in August of 2022 in conjunction with Twitter and LinkedIn accounts.

The domain “www.fisheustrust.org” reflects the project acronym. Unfortunately, it was not possible to use the .eu domain because, as a result of recent regulatory change relating to Brexit, a UK company (i.e. WRG Europe Ltd) cannot register and manage domains with this ending. The domain .org was used as the best alternative to represent the organization that is the FishEUTrust team. It should be noted that it is being explored whether the Coordinator, JSI, can purchase the .eu domain. It will then be possible to set up a redirect from this to the .org domain. This means that all media and branding can retain a .eu domain, which is consistent with other EU projects, whilst a UK organisation can legitimately maintain the website under a .org domain.

The FishEUTrust website provides features such as:

1. An organised, easy-to-navigate space for posting project updates.
2. Fast and effective distribution of information, including project outputs, events, and news.
3. A means to inform stakeholders interested in the project outcomes and tools.
4. A way to communicate effectively with consumers and the general public through items such as informational videos.
5. A means to connect with other related networks and projects (clustering).
6. Connecting with data platforms created within the project.

The website was created using Adobe Dreamweaver, which is a low-level coding application running the latest HTML, PHP, and JavaScript tools for modern, dynamic, responsive websites. The website was carefully colour-coded to match the project branding, creating a fresh, interactive, and engaging experience. The website is fully responsive in the way it adapts to different platforms such as laptops, tablets, and smart phones (including orientation). Each page has also been carefully optimized in terms of meta-text and alt-tags for search engine optimization.

2. Website Content

2.1 Project Homepage

The homepage (Figure 1) has been designed to be attractive and welcoming whilst minimising the amount of information presented to allow easy navigation. Equally, the number of drop-down menu items and sub-menu categories have been kept to a minimum. Each page has “breadcrumb” navigation so the user can know where they are in the page hierarchy. The website is fully searchable.

The upper page consists of a scrolling carousel depicting various related images of fish farming and consumption whilst summarising the objectives of the project (with links to more detailed pages). The lower half and footer of the website contains links to the most recent news articles and events on the dissemination page. There are also quick links, contact information, acknowledgement of the EU funding, and the website’s privacy policy. The website fully links from the footer to the project LinkedIn and Twitter pages. There is also an area to sign up to the project and the newsletter (this is currently inactive until all GDPR regulations have been implemented).

Figure 1: Some segments of the project homepage

2.2. Project Details Page

The “About” menu has three drop-down options: 1) Project Summary 2) Work Packages and 3) Living Labs. The first two items direct to the same page, but at different hashtag locations. The Summary area (Figure 2) is carousel/tab based to allow visitors to quickly access all the most important information about the project. The listed partners have hyperlinks to their homepage.

Figure 2: The Project Overview section

The Work Packages area (Figure 3) has a clickable carousel to show all the Work Package titles. These are linked to detailed descriptions of each Work Packages, which describe each of the sub-tasks, overall duration, primary lead, and primary outputs.

Figure 3: Work Packages section

The Living Labs section is still under construction whilst we await information from the relevant partners. Once this information has been received, the page will contain information regarding the location and activities of the living labs,

how they integrate into the work and objectives of the project, and when appropriate will advertise any open days that may occur.

2.3 The Project Team Page

The Project Team menu has four drop-down menu options: 1) Coordinator, 2) Partners, 3) Management Structure, and 4) Advisory Board. Similarly, these options link to separate hashtag sections on the same page to minimise the amount of “hopping” between web pages. These sections are shown in Figure 4.

The page initially describes the Coordinator (Nives Ogrinc) and her relevant experience. The Consortium is then described by an auto-scrolling carousel. Each partner icon and name links to their organisation website. The management structure is then described by an organigram. Finally, the Advisory Board is still being defined, so this will be added when this is complete.

The screenshot shows the 'Project Team' page of the FishEUTrust website. The page features a navigation menu at the top with options: HOME, ABOUT, PROJECT TEAM, COMMUNICATIONS, and CONTACT US. The main header area displays the FishEUTrust logo and the title 'FishEUTrust Team' over a background image of a coral reef with various fish. Below the header, the page is divided into three main sections:

- Coordinator:** A section featuring a circular portrait of Prof. dr Nives Ogrinc. Text below the portrait identifies her as a professor at the Jozef Stefan International Postgraduate School and describes her research focus on stable isotopes in food and nutrition, mentioning 168 original papers and an h-index of 34.
- Consortium:** A section displaying a horizontal carousel of logos for the project's partners, including UMF, DTU, b-tu, NORCE, EuroFIR, UNIPD, ABT, REDINN, BELIT, Micrux, and JdCA.
- Management Structure:** An organizational chart showing the hierarchy of the project. At the top is the 'SCIENTIFIC & ADMINISTRATIVE MANAGEMENT' box, which includes the 'Coordinator (US)' and the 'Executive Board (EB) (WP leaders)'. This box is flanked by the 'External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB)' on the left and the 'User Stakeholder Group (USG)' on the right. Below this is the 'General Assembly (GA)' box, which includes the 'Programme Manager Officer (PMO)', 'Administrative & Financial Officer', 'Communication & Dissemination (WG)', 'Outreach Officer (NORCE)', 'Gender Officer (EUSTRI)', 'Ethics Officer (EMBO)', and 'Partner Representatives'. The GA is supported by three other management areas: 'DATA MANAGEMENT' (Data Management Board (DS)), 'INNOVATION & EXPLOITATION MANAGEMENT' (Innovation and Exploitation Board (IEB)), and 'General Assembly (GA)'.

Figure 4: Project Team page

2.4 The Communications Page

The Communications menu contains five menu options. This is currently under construction as we await communication-related material. The five options are: 1) News, 2) Events, 3) Digital Media, 4) Articles/Blogs, and 5) Public Reports. As the names suggest, menu items 1 and 2 will link to relevant news and events (such as open days, conferences, etc.). The news items will be linked from the homepage. The Digital Media option will allow the visitor to access a range of static and dynamic media, including a project roll-up/flyer, newsletters, and informational videos. The Articles/Blogs option will allow the visitor to access relevant project or third-party articles related to the project technology. Also, project partners will be encouraged to write more informal blogs about their activities and experiences within the project. Finally, there will be an area where visitors can access public-level deliverable reports and other information such as presentations.

The Communications page is fully searchable by keywords.

2.5 The Contact Page

In addition to the dedicated project email and other general contact details for the coordinating institution (JSI), a “contact us” page is also available so visitors can send messages and queries directly via the website. This is protected by reCAPTCHA.

HOME ABOUT PROJECT TEAM COMMUNICATIONS CONTACT US

Contact Us

HOME → CONTACT US

Get in touch

We are available by email or phone, but if you would like to make an enquiry using our by contact form, please fill in your details below and we will get back to you as soon as possible. Please note the contact page is not active yet. Please call the number below if you have a query.

First Name Last Name Message

E-mail Organisation

I'm not a robot [Privacy Terms](#)

Telephone
Coordinator+ 386 1 588 53 87
Administration+ 386 1 588 53 55

Address
Jožef Stefan Institute, Jamova 39,
1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

E-mail
info-fisheustrust@jsi.si

Figure 5: The contact page

3. Future Website Development

The website will be continuously enhanced and developed throughout the life of the project with new information and functionality added at the appropriate point. Some specific developments are listed below:

1. **Update the Living Labs page:** Once the information has been received from the relevant partners, the Living Labs page will be completed. It will contain information on the location and activities of the Living Labs, how they link to the Work Packages and objectives, and it will also notify website visitors of open days.
2. **Enhancing the dissemination and communication pages:** These will be enhanced when news and articles become available. The consortium will also be encouraged to write blogs where appropriate. It will also be the portal to access public-level reports from the project. Finally, a range of informational material such as project summaries, infographics, and videos will be created and uploaded to this area.
3. **Network formation (clustering):** To improve the connection/networking with other related projects (such as Sea2See), an area will be made to allow confirmed clustering partners to access key information and public project files and documents.
4. **Integrating the website with FishEUTrust data platforms:** As a minimum, the website will contain URLs to the relevant data platforms that are being developed by the partners within WP7. As the project advances, it is hoped that the website can become a secure portal through which data can be pushed/pulled or act as a front-end to these platforms.
5. **Email sign up for newsletters and other services:** On the homepage and contact page, a secure sign-up box will be added to allow interested parties to access the newsletters by email or to just show a general interest in the project activities. With recent updates on GDPR, it will be ensured that all sign-up areas comply to the regulations including use and storage of personal data.

Conclusions

A project website has been developed that is modern, responsive and creates an engaging experience for user. Some functionality of the website is still under development, such as data platform integration, and this will be added at the appropriate juncture within the project. The website will be regularly updated with news, dissemination media, public reports, and related events.

